

Retrieving Images On World Wide Web

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Abstract--

Most web pages typically contain both images and text. However, most current search engines index documents based on text only. In order to facilitate effective search for images on the web, we need to complement text with the visual content of the images. Using text and image content features, a hybrid image retrieval system for World Wide Web is developed in this paper. We first use a text-based image meta-search engine to retrieve images from the Web based on the text information on the image host pages to provide an initial image set.

1. INTRODUCTION

As the diversity and size of digital image collections grow exponentially, efficient image retrieval is becoming increasingly important. In general, current automatic image retrieval systems can be characterized into two categories text-based and image content-based. For text-based image retrieval, the images are first annotated by text and then the text-based Database Management Systems are used to perform image retrieval. In this framework, manual image annotation is extremely laborious and the visual content of images is difficult to be described precisely by a limited set of text terms. To overcome these difficulties, content based image retrieval systems index images by their visual content, such as color, shape, texture etc.

2. HOW TO FIND IMAGES ON THE WEB

Information for finding images on the World Wide Web can come from two sources: the relevant text and the image itself.

Using information from both sources, a program should be able to successfully retrieve requested images.

2.1 Cues from the Text and HTML Source Code

An HTML document is a structured document. There are several places relevant information about image content may be located within the document. These are ordered by the likelihood of the text being useful in an image search.

1. **Image File Names:** File names contain important clues as to the content of the file. In many cases the full URL of an image (e.g. "http://www2.int-evry.fr/~hug/images/marilyn/mmtrans.gif") contains more information than a relative URL (e.g. "mm-trans.gif"), which may be included in the HTML source.

2. **Image Captions:** Often, images have captions that describe the picture. Although HTML does not have an explicit caption tag, captions are often signaled as text that is located within the same center tag as the image(http://www.lib.uchicago.edu/~mozart/Marilyn/monthly.html), within the same cell of a table as an image(http://studentweb.tulane.edu/~llovejo/marilyn/), or within the same paragraph.

3. **ALT= Text:** Image fields in HTML documents may contain a special ALT= section for alternate text which is displayed in the event that the images can not be loaded. This alternate text may briefly describe the content of the image. The alternate text may also give hints as to the intended "goal" of the image. For instance, an image containing an ad for Coca-Cola may have the alternate text "Buy Coca-Cola."

4. **HTML Titles:** The HTML title of the document often provides information about the content of the images contained within the document. For example, the page <http://tomahawk.cf.ac.uk/~scotw/marilyn/page2/page2.html> is entitled “Marilyn Monroe Images - The ventilator scene”, which is highly descriptive of the contents and more descriptive than any other cues that can be found on the page.

5. **Hyperlinks:** The text of a hyperlink usually gives clues about what the link refers to. In many cases, images are referenced by hyperlinks rather than being imbedded within the text of the page. An example of such a link is “Marilyn JPG #21 (Jumping for joy)”, at <http://www.netins.net/showcase/agency/marilyn.html>

6. **Other text:** In addition to those types mentioned above, other text can give cues about the images contained on the page. This text could be used to index the images on the page, with a lower likelihood of reference than the text categories listed above.

2.2 Cues from the Image Content

Although it is clear that the context provided by the surrounding text can produce an effective image search engine, examining the images themselves can substantially enrich the search. The following attributes can be easily obtained from the image header. Grayscale vs. color: Some may wish to search for only color images. While color images can be converted to grayscale, those in search of black-and-white photography will want the real thing.

Image Size: This is usually useful for those who wish to screen out images smaller than a Certain size. · File Type (JPEG, GIF, GIF89, etc.): Some searchers may wish to avoid the compromises in quality introduced by constraints of these formats, especially the limited color palette in the GIF format. GIF89s are animations, and so will often be of separate interest than the other static image formats.

File Size: For those with slow connections or limited RAM or hard drive space, overly large files may be of less interest.

File Date (when present): If someone is looking for newer images, the date can be used to screen out images that are

certainly older than a certain date. Obtaining information beyond that listed above generally requires some image analysis. The most useful sorts of image analysis can be grouped into three overlapping categories:

1. Classifying the image into one of several types (e.g. photograph, hand-drawing, computer generated drawing),
2. Recognizing image structures (e.g. faces, horizons), and
3. Distinguishing specific regions primarily by color/texture attributes (e.g. skin, sky, and foliage)

2.3 Classifying Images

The most important aspect of classification is creating the categories. The authors of an image search engine must either design a system that uses helpful categories, or include a mechanism to allow the user to guide him own search using relevant schema. Ideally, a system would use aspects of both types of categorization. One important classification which can be made is between images that are photographs and hand-drawn and computer-created drawings. In many cases users may wish to find only Photographs of faces, and ignore the many other images that match the search string. Some of these non-photographs may be weeded out because they are too small (e.g. buttons, dividers , arrows). Others, such as image-maps containing text, advertisements, or drawings, must be eliminated on other criteria. Of course, more realistic drawings will be likely to be mistakenly categorized as photographs. Likewise photographs can be thresholded and manipulated in other ways to make them look more like drawings. Nonetheless, we have found that many images can be successfully classified as either drawings or photographs. It may also be possible to separate computer-generated drawings (i.e. those that are artificial-looking, with precisely straight lines and precise color gradients) from hand drawings. There are many other potentially useful categories. Images can be classified as portraits, which can be further classified by the number of people in the image and the amount of the body shown along with the face (close-up, head-and-shoulders, upper-body, etc.). Images can also be classified as indoor or out, and outdoor images can be classified as landscapes. Some

of these categorizations may be best determined by analyzing global statistics, or the statistics of relatively large portions of the image (e.g. photo vs. drawing). Others require other sorts of analysis, which are described below.

2.4 Recognizing Image Structures

There are many types of objects to identify in images, which would aid content-based indexing. Two objects are:

Faces: Face-finding algorithms have recently become fairly successful at finding faces in grayscale photographs. Faces in photographs are often seen upright, with the subject looking at the camera; the easiest situation for face-finding algorithms. Users may wish to find a portrait of a single person, a group photo, or pictures of a crowd” containing many faces. Portraits can be close-ups, head-and shoulders shots, upperbody, or full-body shots; the size and location of the face can differentiate among these choices.

Horizon: A number of systems search images for the presence of a horizon (e.g. the Cypress System). Detecting a horizon in a photograph tells us that the image has been taken outdoors and allows us to roughly classify it as a landscape photograph.

Recognizing Regions by Color/Texture Analysis

Some color and texture analysis may be useful for finding image regions containing skin, sky, foliage, etc. in photographs. Skin may be used for finding faces and determining if images are portraits; it is in itself of interest to some image searchers. Sky and foliage can also be used in image classification. Other less common color textures, including sand, wood, etc., may also be identified. If more classes such as these are created, it may prove useful to look for them only when the context suggests they may be present.

3. TEXT CONTENT BASED RETRIEVAL

Unlike image retrieval from a fixed database, where each image is treated as an independent object, for image retrieval over the Web each image comes along with a host page, which contains a great deal of relevant information about the image. In general, for most of the images on the Web, their

content is more or less related to the content of the host pages. For example, a photo of Mars is found more likely from a page talking about space and planets than from a page talking about pop-music. Therefore, we can use not only the image file names but also the page titles and text terms around the images to index and retrieve the images. The text-based approach is significantly more efficient than the CBIR system on the Internet, in terms of computational cost as well as image transmission and storage cost. Text document retrieval over the Internet has become a routine task for a commercial web search engine. Retrieving images based on text is even simpler since only the portion of the document around the image needs to be searched. We use a meta-search engine to combine several text-based image search engines.

4. IMAGE CONTENT BASED ORDERING

Let's first look at some sample results from the text-based image retrieval over the Internet for text based queries.

Figure 1. Text term search results of some internet image search engines. (a) Relevant results from PicSearch with the term **cup**; (b) Irrelevant results from PicSearch with the term **cup**; (c) Relevant results from Google with the term **cocacola**; (d) Irrelevant results from Google with the term **cocacola**.

We notice that, for a given text query term, the items in the relevant set have similar visual features (e.g. images in group a are similar in shape, images in group c are similar in color), while the images in the irrelevant set differ greatly from each other. A visual feature based clustering method should be able to group the relevant images together thus give a better retrieval performance. The relevant and irrelevant mentioned

above are based on the judgment of the user, who expects to retrieve images related to his query text and his anticipation. Our goal is to analyze the visual content automatically to provide a result that fits both the text description and the user's expectation. We use two visual content-based processing methods on the initial text retrieval results to improve the retrieval performance. One is the unsupervised clustering method and the other is ranking with users relevant feedback.

4.1 Unsupervised clustering

Since the expected relevant images are likely to be similar to each other in content, we can perform an unsupervised clustering to group them together. A color histogram in the HSV color space described in the scalable Color Descriptor in MPEG 7 is used as the feature vector. We choose k-means algorithm for the feature clustering.

4.2 Ranking with relevant feedback

Another reordering approach is to bring some "typical" images to the user and re-rank all the items based on the user's relevant feedback. The selection of "typical" images could be some representative items of each cluster. It could also be some top ranked items by the text-based retrieval. The user could select one or more items to express his anticipation.

5. THE META-SEARCH ENGINE IMPLEMENTATION

We now can build an efficient image retrieval engine on the Internet based on the two-step text and visual content-based approach. We implement the first step of our system (text content based query) as a meta-search engine, which sends queries to other text-based image search engines and summarizes their results to build an initial image set for later image content based processing. This brings us a more comprehensive initial data set with a higher recall than using a single search engine.

Although the precision is comparatively low, it can be greatly improved in later steps.

Figure 2 shows the system architecture of the hybrid meta-search engine. We can summarize the image retrieval procedure as follows:

- 1 User inputs a few query text terms to the browser.
- 2 The Query Translator extracts the query terms from the HTTP request, and then translates the query terms into the input format for each text-based image search engines, such as Google Image Search, PicSearch, AltaVista Image Search, and passes to the Page Crawler.
- 3 The Page Crawler sends the query to each search engine and collects the HTML files containing the URLs of images retrieved by the search engines, then parses the HTML files to obtain the individual URL.
- 4 The Result Collator merges the results and shows the first page of retrieved images and URLs to the user, and at the same time, send all the URLs to the Image Crawler.
- 5 Using the URLs, the Image Crawler retrieves the images from the Internet to construct the initial image set;
- 6 Feature Extractor computes the image content feature vectors for all images in the initial image set.
- 7 Upon the user's new request, cluster the image set using the feature vectors and k-means algorithm. Return the clustered images in a new HTML file for display in the user browser.
- 8 Based on the feedback image(s) selected by the user; compute the distance of feature vectors between the feedback image(s) and the images in the initial image set. Re-rank the images according to the distance and display the re-ranked images to the user.

5.1 Text-based Image Retrieval

Five terms, "sun", "forest", "ocean", "CocaCola", and "desert", are used as the query terms. For each query, the first 60

Figure 2. Architecture of the hybrid image retrieval system.

images returned from text-based image metasearch engine are chosen as the initial image set (I). A relevant set (R) from the initial image set is defined as the set of images containing the subject of the query term. (For example, the relevant set for “forest” is the set of images containing forest.) The number of relevant images, |R|, in the initial image set for each query is shown in Table 1. The results show that the text-based retrieval can provide many relevant images in the first step, but the precision is low.

Table 1. Number of relevant images for five queries.

Term	sun	forest	ocean	cocacola	desert
R	34	30	35	30	28

5.2 Content-based Image Clustering

Figure 3. Clustering result for the query term “CocaCola”.

Reordering the clusters by precision, the recall (r) and precision (p) for each cluster are shown in Table 2.

The 60 images in the initial set are clustered into 4 folders based on the color feature.

In Table 2, C1 is the most relevant cluster with the highest precision, and C4 is the most irrelevant cluster. Referring to the definition of recall and precision in (1) and (2), here, R contains all the relevant images within the 60 images retrieved by the text-based method, A is the cluster set, and Ra is the relevant image set in each cluster.

		C1	C2	C3	C4
“sun”	p (%)	100	29	15	11
	r (%)	43	14	21	21
“forest”	p (%)	73	33	19	17
	r (%)	73	3	13	3
“ocean”	p (%)	86	83	22	17
	r (%)	71	14	11	3
“CocaCola”	p (%)	100	52	33	0
	r (%)	50	43	7	0
“desert”	p (%)	100	89	36	0
	r (%)	18	32	53	0
average	p (%)	92	57	25	9
	r (%)	51	21	21	7

Table 2.

6. CONCLUSION

The main purpose of this paper is to provide a WWW based image retrieval. We perform a efficient and truly realizable approach for text-based meta-search to obtain an initial image set with relatively high recall rate and recall and precision for each cluster low precision rate. There are three ways to combine the text-based method and the visual content-based method: use the text-based method first; use the visual content-based method first; use the two methods at the same time. The key to the success of this system is using the first approach.

7. REFERENCES

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